

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

D4.1 REPORT ON REGIONAL CAPACITY: STAKEHOLDER PESTLE ANALYSIS

28/11/2023

Under Approval by CINEA / European Union

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D4.1 REPORT ON REGIONAL CAPACITY: STAKEHOLDER PESTLE ANALYSIS

BASELINE ASSESSMENT OF PESTLE FACTORS IN THE RESTORE4LIFE IMPLEMENTATION SITES

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Abstract	The report presents the results from PESTLE analyses with stakeholders at the four project Implementation Sites where restoration actions are planned. The overall importance of various socio-economic and environmental factors was assessed as broadly similar in all countries. However there were some clear differences between EU Member States and non-EU Serbia, while Austria and Slovakia had rather a different outlook compared with Romania. None of the sites had people living within them so there were no directly concerned local communities.
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11	Asociatia WWF Romania	WWF Romania	RO
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20	Javna Ustanova Univerzitet Crne Gore Podgorica	UOM	MK
21	University of Sarajevo	UNSA	BA
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30	Ministerul Mediului, Apelor si Padurilor	MMAP	RO
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Within the Restore4Life project, there is a task (WP4.1) to contact local business owners and entrepreneurs at each of the four implementation sites to conduct PESTLE analyses to discover the limitations of and comparative advantages and further development options for local sustainable use of restored wetlands using nature-based solutions and increasing revenue to local communities. PESTLE analyses assess the key external factors (Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental) that influence an organisation or help to solve a particular problem.

The report presents the results from PESTLE analyses with stakeholders at the project Implementation Sites where restoration actions are planned in Austria, Romania, Serbia and Slovakia. The overall importance of various socio-economic and environmental factors was assessed as broadly similar in all countries. However there were some clear differences between EU Member States and non-EU Serbia, while Austria and Slovakia had rather a different outlook compared with Romania. None of the sites had people living within them so there were no directly concerned local communities.

Thus the PESTLE data collected in this preliminary study at the four Implementation Sites, taking account of the relatively small numbers of participants that were not randomly selected, suggested the following conclusions can be tentatively made:

- For the main factors of the conventional socio-economic PESTLE, the results largely agreed with current surveys of public opinion in Europe;
- For those factors chosen for relevance to the Restore4Life project, only one was rated as good: political will to invest in NBS at Vlasina (though this contrasted with a poor rating for political will for NBS);
- The attractiveness of the four sites for NBS businesses could be ranked as best in Vlasina and worst in March, though none of the sites seems especially outstanding and any initiative would meet a large range of challenges for any entrepreneur.

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ABBREVIATIONS

NbS Nature-based solutions

1 INTRODUCTION

The Restore4life project (Restoration of wetland complexes as life supporting systems in the Danube Basin) is a new Horizon Europe funded project that supports the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters. The Mission aims to protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. The Mission’s new approach will address the ocean and waters as one system and play a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature.

Restore4Life itself will develop a “Restore4Life Wetland Restoration Decision Support System” at the Danube Basin level. The service will be based on a shared vision for wetland restoration, including co-creation and co-development of tools that will allow local stakeholders and actors to be actively involved in restoration works and will help local businesses to adopt new activities through nature-based solutions supported by new generation of data analysis tools.

The project will run for 48 months and is led by the University of Bucharest. The consortium consists of a total of 31 organizations including 5 local and national authorities, 21 academic and research institutions, 3 NGOs and 2 SMEs.

1.1 RESTORE4LIFE IMPLEMENTATION SITES

The four Restore4Life project locations are shown in Figure 1 and briefly described in Table 1.

FIGURE 1: LOCATION OF IMPLEMENTATION SITES WITHIN THE DANUBE BASIN

TABLE 1: BRIEF OVERVIEW OF IMPLEMENTATION SITES

Code, Name	Features	
IS 1 March - Thaya Floodplains, AT/SK	River-floodplain systems with various side arms and backwaters, floodplain forests. Restoration of a dried channel to restore flow to an internal lake.	
IS 2 Rudava, SK	Tributary of March river; river-floodplain with oxbow lakes. Restoration of flow in former river channel.	
IS 3 Vlasina, SRB	River-floodplain with wet meadows. Restoration of wet meadow habitats.	
IS 4 Enisala Channel, RO	Part of the Razim - Sinoe lagoon complex, key spawning area for <i>Sander lucioperca</i> . Restoration of fish spawning area.	

1.2 GENERATING LOCAL BUSINESS ACTIVITIES & REVENUE IN RESTORED ECOSYSTEMS

Wetlands provide opportunities to conduct ecologically sustainable business due to their outstanding aquatic and terrestrial biomass and food production, capacity for carbon sequestration, habitat quality and diversity, and potential for tourism.

Within the Restore4Life project, there is a task to contact local business owners and entrepreneurs at each of the implementation sites to discover the limitations of and comparative advantages and further development options for local sustainable use of restored wetlands using PESTLE analysis. PESTLE analyses¹ assess the key external factors (Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental) that influence an organisation, including environmental bodies such as the Worldwide Fund for Nature WWF (Pamplona, 2019)², or help to solve a particular problem for example the impacts of companies and public actors dealing with big data technologies in the bioeconomy sector³ or the installation of a new water intake structure in Serbia⁴.

Particular emphasis is laid on exploring market demands, needed investments and financing instruments for market access. The work will assess the availability within each region of essential business capacity and support infrastructures such as energy supply, transport, storage, trading houses, communications, and finance offices, as well as enable exchange of experiences among regions.

In this study, PESTLE analyses were conducted with stakeholders from the four Restore4Life Implementation Sites to assess conditions and opportunities for conducting ecologically sustainable business in the respective regions, especially those arising from the proposed restoration activities. Follow-up studies will be conducted in additional monitoring sites and associated regions when these sites have been defined.

¹ <https://www.cjpd.org/en/knowledge/factsheets/pestle-analysis-factsheet/>

² <https://studylib.net/doc/25425450/wwf-final-paper.pdf>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b77bf202&appId=PPGMS>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-012-0077-2>

2 METHODOLOGY

The PESTLE analyses were carried out in conjunction with Information Workshops organised under the citizen science Work Package of the project. The participants were invited by the local coordinators for each Implementation Site and comprised local officials, businesses, protected area authorities and scientists. The PESTLE questionnaire used is presented in Table 2, the conventional content having been extended to take account of key project interests such as biodiversity enhancement, nature-based solutions and financial incentives for nature conservation.

Each PESTLE session lasted about 2 hours during which the participants were presented with the questionnaire (translated into the local language) and the scoring system. The participants raised their hands to indicate their preferred score for the importance or state of each issue on scale of 1 to 5 as shown below

Potential Impact	Present Condition
1 = very low	1 = very good, measures in place and well enforced
2 = low	2 = good, measures in place, mostly enforced
3 = moderate, needs attention	3 = moderate, measures in place, poorly enforced
4 = high, should be considered	4 = bad, measures in place, no enforcement
5 = very high, must be considered	5 = very bad, no measures in place

The scores were recorded live in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet that calculated the cumulative score for each issue and the percentage of the maximum possible score (allowing for occasional abstentions or zero votes). At the end of the session, the Excel spreadsheet displayed the results as bar charts to give immediate feedback on the results to the participants and allow for some discussion of them.

The results from the four PESTLE are given in Tables 3 to 6, and depicted as bar charts in Figures 3 to 6. The figures in the table are for the number of participants voting for that score, or abstaining (0 vote).

TABLE 2: RESTORE4LIFE PESTLE DATA FORM

Factor	Features	Potential consequences	Scoring
Politics	Government reform	New laws and regulations	Impact
	Changed funding schemes	Business viability improves	Impact
	Conflicts in the political area	Uncertain political situation for obtaining permits	Impact
	Corruption	Increased cost of business from corruption	Impact
	Poor security	High risk of theft, damage etc	Impact
	Bureaucratic burden	Obstacles to business development	Impact
	Supportive political environment	Access to policy makers	Impact
	Policy endorsement of NBS	Political will to invest in NBS	Impact
Economics	Inflation rate	Raised input prices	Impact
	Interest rates	Higher cost of loans	Impact
	Tax rates	Higher cost of business	Impact
	Access to funding / investment	Impact on business development	Impact
	Exchange rate volatility	Gains / losses in sales	Impact
	Employment market	Difficulty / cost of hiring staff	Impact
	Disposable income	Increase / decrease of sales	Impact
	Competition	Price wars, quality standards affected	Impact
	Policy measures	Subsidies	Impact
	Competing land use priorities	Conflicts between different land users	Impact
	Converting NBS benefits into revenue	Financing models that reduce uncertainty	Impact
	Demand for “green finance”	Opportunities for NBS business development	Impact
	Investor demands	Repayment of loans / dividends	Impact
Social	Education	Availability of skilled staff	Impact
	Cultural norms	Atypical working practices	Impact
	Demographics	Junior staff availability	Impact
	Consumer opinions and attitudes	Change of consumption patterns	Impact
	Environmental awareness	Change of public awareness of NBS concept	Impact
	Perception of NBS business	Responsible company regarding biodiversity	Impact
Technology	New production technologies	Need to adapt and invest capital	Impact
	Social media communications	Need to manage messaging / advertisements	Impact
	Infrastructure status	Access to markets	Impact
	Measuring the impact of NBS	Infrastructure, equipment, technology for monitoring	Impact
Legal	Laws and policies in force	Ability to obtain permits, licences	Impact
	Employment law	Health and safety equipment, procedures	Condition
	Consumer protection	Product quality assurance procedures	Condition
	Environmental regulations	Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts	Condition
Environment	Physical geography / climate	Seasonal conditions	Impact
	Use of hazardous materials	Handling / disposal procedures in place	Condition
	Ecological features	Protection of habitats and species	Condition
	Ownership - specific regulations	Rules and standards for both private/public ownership of natural resource	Condition
	Industry-specific regulations	Rules and standards to be met	Condition
	Environmental risk	Rules and standards to assess risk to be met	Condition

3 RESULTS

TABLE 3: PESTLE ISSUE SCORES FOR MARCH

No. Participants 16

Date of meeting 02/11/2023

Features	Issues	1	2	3	4	5	0	Max score	Score	% Max score	% no vote
Politics											
Government reform	New laws and regulations	0	0	3	9	0	4	60	45	75.0	25.0
Changed funding schemes	Business viability improves	0	0	9	1	0	6	50	31	62.0	37.5
Conflicts in the political area	Uncertain situation for obtaining permits	0	2	6	3	0	5	55	34	61.8	31.3
Corruption	Increased cost of business	0	11	2	0	0	3	65	28	43.1	18.8
Poor security	High risk of theft, damage etc	6	9	0	0	0	1	75	24	32.0	6.3
Bureaucratic burden	Obstacles to business development	0	0	1	12	1	2	70	56	80.0	12.5
Supportive political environment	Access to policy makers	0	9	5	0	0	2	70	33	47.1	12.5
Policy endorsement of NBS	Political will to invest in NBS	0	0	5	9	0	2	70	51	72.9	12.5
Economics											
Inflation rate	Raised input prices	0	0	7	4	0	5	55	37	67.3	31.3
Interest rates	Higher cost of loans	0	0	3	5	0	8	40	29	72.5	50.0
Tax rates	Higher cost of business	0	0	2	4	1	9	35	27	77.1	56.3
Access to funding / investment	Impact on business development	0	0	3	3	0	10	30	21	70.0	62.5
Exchange rate volatility	Gains / losses in sales	0	5	2	0	0	9	35	16	45.7	56.3
Employment market	Difficulty / cost of hiring staff	0	0	5	7	0	4	60	43	71.7	25.0
Disposable income	Increase / decrease of sales	0	0	10	4	0	2	70	46	65.7	12.5
Competition	Price wars, quality standards affected	0	1	8	2	0	5	55	34	61.8	31.3
Policy measures	Subsidies	0	0	8	2	0	6	50	32	64.0	37.5
Competing land use priorities	Conflicts between different land users	0	0	0	14	0	2	70	56	80.0	12.5
Converting NBS benefits into revenue	Financing models that reduce uncertainty	0	0	0	6	4	6	50	44	88.0	37.5
Demand for "green finance"	Opportunities for NBS business development	0	0	0	6	5	5	55	49	89.1	31.3
Social Issues											
Education	Availability of skilled staff	0	0	10	1	2	3	65	44	67.7	18.8
Cultural norms	Atypical working practices	0	0	6	5	0	5	55	38	69.1	31.3
Demographics	Junior staff availability	0	1	5	8	0	2	70	49	70.0	12.5
Consumer opinions and attitudes	Change of consumption patterns	0	6	7	0	0	3	65	33	50.8	18.8
Environmental awareness	Change of public awareness of NBS concept	0	1	10	4	0	1	75	48	64.0	6.3
Perception of NBS business	Responsible company regarding biodiversity	0	0	5	8	0	3	65	47	72.3	18.8
Technology											
New production technologies	Need to adapt and invest capital	0	2	12	0	0	2	70	40	57.1	12.5
Social media communications	Need to manage messaging / advertisements	0	3	8	1	0	4	60	34	56.7	25.0
Infrastructure status	Access to markets	0	9	3	1	0	3	65	31	47.7	18.8
Legislation											
Laws and policies in force	Ability to obtain permits, licences	0	0	7	4	0	5	55	37	67.3	31.3
Employment law	Health and safety equipment, procedures	0	12	1	0	0	3	65	27	41.5	18.8
Consumer protection	Product quality assurance procedures	0	12	1	0	0	3	65	27	41.5	18.8
Environmental regulations	Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts	0	4	11	0	0	1	75	41	54.7	6.3
Environment											
Physical geography / climate	Seasonal conditions	0	0	8	5	0	3	65	44	67.7	18.8
Use of hazardous materials	Handling / disposal procedures	0	1	5	5	0	5	55	37	67.3	31.3

Features	Issues	1	2	3	4	5	0	Max score	Score	% Max score	% no vote
Politics											
Ecological features	Care for protected habitats and species	0	5	9	1	0	1	75	41	54.7	6.3

FIGURE 2: CHARTS OF PESTLE SCORES FROM MARCH, SHOWING THE 60% BOUNDARY

Politics

Economics

Social Factors

Technology

Legislation

Environment

TABLE 4: PESTLE ISSUE SCORES FOR RUDAVA

No. Participants 26, 16 after lunch

Date of meeting 31/10/2023

Features	Issues	1	2	3	4	5	0	Max score	Score	% Max score	% no vote
Politics											
Government reform	New laws and regulations	0	0	0	14	12	0	130	116	89.2	0.0
Changed funding schemes	Business viability improves	0	15	10	0	0	1	125	60	48.0	3.8
Conflicts in the political area	Uncertain situation for obtaining permits	2	11	12	0	0	1	125	60	48.0	3.8
Corruption	Increased cost of business	0	0	4	18	3	1	125	99	79.2	3.8
Poor security	High risk of theft, damage etc	0	11	11	4	0	0	130	71	54.6	0.0
Bureaucratic burden	Obstacles to business development	0	2	8	15	0	1	125	88	70.4	3.8
Supportive political environment	Access to policy makers	0	1	17	7	1	0	130	86	66.2	0.0
Policy endorsement of NBS	Political will to invest in NBS	1	7	11	5	0	2	120	68	56.7	7.7
Economics											
Inflation rate	Raised input prices	0	0	2	22	2	0	130	104	80.0	0.0
Interest rates	Higher cost of loans	0	0	17	7	0	2	120	79	65.8	7.7
Tax rates	Higher cost of business	0	0	19	7	0	0	130	85	65.4	0.0
Access to funding / investment	Impact on business development	0	0	22	4	0	0	130	82	63.1	0.0
Exchange rate volatility	Gains / losses in sales	0	5	14	1	0	6	100	56	56.0	23.1
Employment market	Difficulty / cost of hiring staff	0	2	10	13	1	0	130	91	70.0	0.0
Disposable income	Increase / decrease of sales	0	0	10	14	0	2	120	86	71.7	7.7
Competition	Price wars, quality standards affected	0	1	19	3	0	3	115	71	61.7	11.5
Policy measures	Subsidies	0	1	17	6	0	2	120	77	64.2	7.7
Competing land use priorities	Conflicts between different land users	0	0	16	8	0	2	120	80	66.7	7.7
Converting NBS benefits into revenue	Financing models that reduce uncertainty	0	1	13	7	0	5	105	69	65.7	19.2
Demand for "green finance"	Opportunities for NBS business development	0	1	8	14	0	3	115	82	71.3	11.5
Social Issues											
Education	Availability of skilled staff	0	0	9	15	0	2	120	87	72.5	7.7
Cultural norms	Atypical working practices	5	17	0	0	0	4	110	39	35.5	15.4
Demographics	Junior staff availability	0	4	16	4	1	1	125	77	61.6	3.8
Consumer opinions and attitudes	Change of consumption patterns	0	1	18	4	0	3	115	72	62.6	11.5
Environmental awareness	Change of public awareness of NBS concept	0	1	14	9	0	2	120	80	66.7	7.7
Perception of NBS business	Responsible company regarding biodiversity	0	2	11	10	0	3	115	77	67.0	11.5
Technology											
New production technologies	Need to adapt and invest capital	0	13	3	0	0	1	80	35	43.8	6.3
Social media communications	Need to manage messaging / advertisements	0	3	10	3	0	1	80	48	60.0	6.3
Infrastructure status	Access to markets	0	1	5	10	0	1	80	57	71.3	6.3
Legislation											
Laws and policies in force	Ability to obtain permits, licences	0	8	4	4	0	1	80	44	55.0	6.3
Employment law	Health and safety equipment, procedures	1	15	1	0	0	0	85	34	40.0	0.0
Consumer protection	Product quality assurance procedures	1	10	5	0	0	1	80	36	45.0	6.3
Environmental regulations	Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts	0	9	8	0	0	0	85	42	49.4	0.0
Environment											
Physical geography / climate	Seasonal conditions	0	0	4	12	1	0	85	65	76.5	0.0
Use of hazardous materials	Handling / disposal procedures	0	6	10	1	0	0	85	46	54.1	0.0
Ecological features	Care for protected habitats and species	0	2	12	1	0	2	75	44	58.7	12.5

FIGURE 3: CHARTS OF PESTLE SCORES FROM RUDAVA, SHOWING THE 60% BOUNDARY

Social Factors

Technology

Legislation

Environment

TABLE 5: PESTLE ISSUE SCORES FOR VLASINA

No Participants 16

Date of meeting 25/10/2023

Features	Issues	1	2	3	4	5	0	Max score	Score	% Max score	% no vote
Politics											
Government reform	New laws and regulations			1	12	3		65	51	78.5	18.8
Changed funding schemes	Business viability improves			5	6	5		55	39	70.9	31.3
Conflicts in the political area	Uncertain situation for obtaining permits	1	4	8		3		65	46	70.8	18.8
Corruption	Increased cost of business			4	9	3		65	61	93.8	18.8
Poor security	High risk of theft, damage etc	6	5		1	4		60	20	33.3	25.0
Bureaucratic burden	Obstacles to business development			1	10	2	3	65	53	81.5	18.8
Supportive political environment	Access to policy makers			6	4		6	50	34	68.0	37.5
Policy endorsement of NBS	Political will to invest in NBS	1	10				5	55	21	38.2	31.3
Economics											
Inflation rate	Raised input prices		1	9	3		3	65	41	63.1	18.8
Interest rates	Higher cost of loans		1		10		5	55	42	76.4	31.3
Tax rates	Higher cost of business			2	7	2	5	55	44	80.0	31.3
Access to funding / investment	Impact on business development		1	1	6	2	6	50	39	78.0	37.5
Exchange rate volatility	Gains / losses in sales	6	4				6	50	14	28.0	37.5
Employment market	Difficulty / cost of hiring staff		1	4		4	7	45	34	75.6	43.8
Disposable income	Increase / decrease of sales			7	2	1	6	50	34	68.0	37.5
Competition	Price wars, quality standards affected		6	3	1		6	50	25	50.0	37.5
Policy measures	Subsidies		6	3			7	45	21	46.7	43.8
Competing land use priorities	Conflicts between different land users			6	7		3	65	46	70.8	18.8
Converting NBS benefits into revenue	Financing models that reduce uncertainty		4	2			10	30	14	46.7	62.5
Demand for "green finance"	Opportunities for NBS business development		5	3			8	40	19	47.5	50.0
Social Issues											
Education	Availability of skilled staff			11			5	55	33	60.0	31.3
Cultural norms	Atypical working practices		16				0	80	32	40.0	0.0
Demographics	Junior staff availability			3	9	1	3	65	50	76.9	18.8
Consumer opinions and attitudes	Change of consumption patterns			10	3		3	65	42	64.6	18.8
Environmental awareness	Change of public awareness of NBS concept		8	6			2	70	34	48.6	12.5
Perception of NBS business	Responsible company regarding biodiversity		8				8	40	16	40.0	50.0
Technology											
New production technologies	Need to adapt and invest capital		9	2			5	55	24	43.6	31.3
Social media communications	Need to manage messaging / advertisements						16	0	0	0.0	100.0
Infrastructure status	Access to markets		1		8		7	45	34	75.6	43.8
Legislation											
Laws and policies in force	Ability to obtain permits, licences				1		15	5	4	80.0	93.8
Employment law	Health and safety equipment, procedures			13	1		2	70	43	61.4	12.5
Consumer protection	Product quality assurance procedures						16	0	0	0.0	100.0
Environmental regulations	Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts			2	2		12	20	14	70.0	75.0
Environment											
Physical geography / climate	Seasonal conditions			8	4		4	60	40	66.7	25.0
Use of hazardous materials	Handling / disposal procedures			8	1		7	45	28	62.2	43.8
Ecological features	Care for protected habitats and species			4	12		0	80	60	75.0	0.0

FIGURE 4: CHARTS OF PESTLE SCORES FROM VLASINA, SHOWING THE 60% BOUNDARY

TABLE 6: PESTLE ISSUE SCORES FOR ENISALA

No Participants 17

Date of meeting 20/10/2023

Features	Issues	1	2	3	4	5	0	Max score	Score	% Max score	% no vote
Politics											
Government reform	New laws and regulations				5	10	2	75	70	93.3	11.8
Changed funding schemes	Business viability improves				4	7	6	55	51	92.7	35.3
Conflicts in the political area	Uncertain situation for obtaining permits	1	13	2			1	80	49	61.3	5.9
Corruption	Increased cost of business			9	1	2	5	60	41	68.3	29.4
Poor security	High risk of theft, damage etc		11	4			2	75	34	45.3	11.8
Bureaucratic burden	Obstacles to business development	1	2	10			4	65	35	53.8	23.5
Supportive political environment	Access to policy makers		1	10	4		2	75	48	64.0	11.8
Policy endorsement of NBS	Political will to invest in NBS	1	7	5			4	65	30	46.2	23.5
Economics											
Inflation rate	Raised input prices			14	1		2	75	46	61.3	11.8
Interest rates	Higher cost of loans				15	1	1	80	65	81.3	5.9
Tax rates	Higher cost of business			4	13		0	85	64	75.3	0.0
Access to funding / investment	Impact on business development			2	13	1	1	80	63	78.8	5.9
Exchange rate volatility	Gains / losses in sales			14			3	70	42	60.0	17.6
Employment market	Difficulty / cost of hiring staff			4	10		3	70	52	74.3	17.6
Disposable income	Increase / decrease of sales			17			0	85	51	60.0	0.0
Competition	Price wars, quality standards affected		13	4			0	85	38	44.7	0.0
Policy measures	Subsidies		2	6	4		5	60	38	63.3	29.4
Competing land use priorities	Conflicts between different land users		5	9			3	70	37	52.9	17.6
Converting NBS benefits into revenue	Financing models that reduce uncertainty		3	3			11	30	15	50.0	64.7
Demand for "green finance"	Opportunities for NBS business development	1	10	2			4	65	27	41.5	23.5
Social Issues											
Education	Availability of skilled staff	7	7				3	70	21	30.0	17.6
Cultural norms	Atypical working practices	2	12	2	1		0	85	36	42.4	0.0
Demographics	Junior staff availability			15	1		1	80	49	61.3	5.9
Consumer opinions and attitudes	Change of consumption patterns		2	13			2	75	43	57.3	11.8
Environmental awareness	Change of public awareness of NBS concept		3	13			1	80	45	56.3	5.9
Perception of NBS business	Responsible company regarding biodiversity										
Technology											
New production technologies	Need to adapt and invest capital		2	9	2	1	3	70	44	62.9	17.6
Social media communications	Need to manage messaging / advertisements		2	13	1		1	80	47	58.8	5.9
Infrastructure status	Access to markets										
Legislation											
Laws and policies in force	Ability to obtain permits, licences			13	2		2	75	47	62.7	11.8
Employment law	Health and safety equipment, procedures		4	9			4	65	35	53.8	23.5
Consumer protection	Product quality assurance procedures			6	9		2	75	54	72.0	11.8
Environmental regulations	Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts										
Environment											
Physical geography / climate	Seasonal conditions		4	9	2		2	75	43	57.3	11.8
Use of hazardous materials	Handling / disposal procedures			4	8		5	60	44	73.3	29.4
Ecological features	Care for protected habitats and species				5	10	2	75	70	93.3	11.8

FIGURE 5: CHARTS OF PESTLE SCORES FROM ENISALA, SHOWING THE 60% BOUNDARY

4 DISCUSSION

In general, the scores overall unsurprisingly took a normal distribution with a tendency for the scores to cluster around the middle, with far fewer scores for either the highest or lowest categories, and a significant level of abstentions, especially in March and Vlasina. (Figure 6). There was a slight preference to select the higher impact or less good condition scores (4 and 5) than the lower impact or better condition ones (1 and 2). This pattern is also apparent when analysing the distribution of scores that are below 40% or exceed 60% of the maximum for each issue (Table 6) where more pessimism than optimism was expressed across the sites.

FIGURE 6: TOTAL PESTLE SCORES BY SITES

Table 6 summaries the percentage of the maximum score for each issue for all sites (colour coded for the number of sites scoring above 60%), as well as the level of abstentions (shaded for 0 votes at over 25%, 50% or 75%). In general, the overall number of significant issues across the four sites was similar, ranging from 21 at Enisala to 24 at March. The lowest level of abstentions over 25% for any issue occurred at Rudava (0), followed by Enisala (3), March (14) and Vlasina (22). Indeed, Vlasina had such a high rate of abstentions that many issues were hard to interpret.

TABLE 7 : TOTAL SCORES FOR ISSUES AS A % OF THE MAXIMUM SCORE BY SITE

Colour code for no. of sites with the same score Abstention rates

	0
	1
	2

3
4

>25%
>50%
>75%

	March score	March 0-vote	Rudava score	Rudava 0-vote	Vlasina score	Vlasina 0-vote	Enisala score	Enisala 0-vote	>60%	<40%
POLITICS										
Government reform	75.0	25.0	89.2	-	78.5	18.8	93.3	11.8		
Changed funding schemes	62.0	37.5	48.0	3.8	70.9	31.3	92.7	35.3		
Uncertain situation for obtaining permits	61.8	31.3	48.0	3.8	70.8	18.8	61.3	5.9		
Increased cost of business from corruption	43.1	18.8	79.2	3.8	93.8	18.8	68.3	29.4		
High risk of theft, damage etc	32.0	6.3	54.6	-	33.3	25.0	45.3	11.8		
Bureaucratic burden	80.0	12.5	70.4	3.8	81.5	18.8	53.8	23.5		
Supportive political environment for NBS	47.1	12.5	66.2	-	68.0	37.5	64.0	11.8		
Political will to invest in NBS	72.9	12.5	56.7	7.7	38.2	31.3	46.2	23.5		
ECONOMICS										
Inflation rate: Raised input prices	67.3	31.3	80.0	-	63.1	18.8	61.3	11.8		
Interest rates: Higher cost of loans	72.5	50.0	65.8	7.7	76.4	31.3	81.3	5.9		
Tax rates: Higher cost of business	77.1	56.3	65.4	-	80.0	31.3	75.3	-		
Access to funding / investment	70.0	62.5	63.1	-	78.0	37.5	78.8	5.9		
Exchange rate volatility	45.7	56.3	56.0	23.1	28.0	37.5	60.0	17.6		
Difficulty / cost of hiring staff	71.7	25.0	70.0	-	75.6	43.8	74.3	17.6		
Disposable income	65.7	12.5	71.7	7.7	68.0	37.5	60.0	-		
Competition	61.8	31.3	61.7	11.5	50.0	37.5	44.7	-		
Policy measures	64.0	37.5	64.2	7.7	46.7	43.8	63.3	29.4		
Conflicts between different land users	80.0	12.5	66.7	7.7	70.8	18.8	52.9	17.6		
Converting NBS benefits into revenue	88.0	37.5	65.7	19.2	46.7	62.5	50.0	64.7		
Opportunities for NBS business development	89.1	31.3	71.3	11.5	47.5	50.0	41.5	23.5		
SOCIAL ISSUES										
Availability of skilled staff	67.7	18.8	72.5	7.7	60.0	31.3	30.0	17.6		
Cultural norms: Atypical working practices	69.1	31.3	35.5	15.4	40.0	-	42.4	-		
Junior staff availability	70.0	12.5	61.6	3.8	76.9	18.8	61.3	5.9		
Change of consumption patterns	50.8	18.8	62.6	11.5	64.6	18.8	57.3	11.8		
Change of public awareness of NBS concept	64.0	6.3	66.7	7.7	48.6	12.5	56.3	5.9		
Responsible company regarding biodiversity	72.3	18.8	67.0	11.5	40.0	50.0	-	100.0		
TECHNOLOGY										
Need to adapt and invest capital	57.1	12.5	43.8	6.3	43.6	31.3	62.9	17.6		
Need to manage messaging / advertisements	56.7	25.0	60.0	6.3	-	100.0	67.5	5.9		
Access to markets	47.7	18.8	71.3	6.3	75.6	43.8	58.8	5.9		
LEGISLATION										
Ability to obtain permits, licences	67.3	31.3	55.0	6.3	80.0	93.8	62.7	11.8		
Health and safety equipment, procedures	41.5	18.8	40.0	-	61.4	12.5	60.0	23.5		
Product quality assurance procedures	41.5	18.8	45.0	6.3	-	100.0	53.8	23.5		
Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts	54.7	6.3	49.4	-	70.0	75.0	72.0	11.8		
ENVIRONMENT										
Seasonal conditions	67.7	18.8	76.5	-	66.7	25.0	67.1	17.6		
Handling hazardous materials	67.3	31.3	54.1	-	62.2	43.8	57.3	11.8		
Care for protected habitats and species	54.7	6.3	58.7	12.5	75.0	-	73.3	29.4		
Total number of important issues	24		23		23		21			
Total number of 0 votes 25% or more		14		-		22		3		

4.1 POLITICS

In the Political arena, only government reform (implying changes in legislation, regulations and funding) was considered to have a highly significant impact across the sites. No sites reported significant concerns

over safety and business security (potential for thefts and vandalism). Only March considered that the political will to invest in NBS was very low. Most other issues fell in the middle range of importance across the sites.

4.2 ECONOMICS

In the Economics field, it is interesting that March and Rudava had exactly the same set of significant issues, meaning all of them bar exchange rate volatility. In general nearly all issues were scored as significant and shared across three or four sites; exchange rate volatility was a concern only at Enisala. Thus, the economic conditions across the sites were rather uniformly poor, although only March and Rudava scored NBS opportunities as bad.

4.3 SOCIAL ISSUES

The pattern of concerns for social issues across the sites was quite variable, except that all sites reported the availability of recruiting junior staff problematic (reflecting a general trend of demographic change and rural depopulation in Europe). Apart from March, there was a general tolerance of atypical working practices resulting from cultural differences. As for Economics, March and Rudava had similar social issue concerns, and most number of them, although they both considered that NBS awareness and responsible company behaviour in relation to biodiversity was in a good condition (even if, as reported above, economic support was lacking).

4.4 TECHNOLOGY

The role of technology in business development, from capital investment to use of social media, was recognised mostly at a moderate level. Rudava and Vlasina reported access to markets (transport infrastructure) as an important issue.

4.5 LEGISLATION

Assessing the influence of legislation on local business posed difficulties for participants at Vlasina for unclear reasons. Otherwise, the importance of the issues were generally scored as moderate with no obvious pattern between the sites.

4.6 ENVIRONMENT

Seasonal conditions (associated with climate change) were recognised as important at all the sites. The handling of hazardous materials (e.g. expired pesticides and industrial waste) was considered to be moderately successful. Participants at March and Ruda shared the view that care for protected habitats and species is a good state, while at Vlasina and Enisala it was considered to be in a bad state.

5 CONCLUSIONS

From the PESTLE data collected in this preliminary study at the four Implementation Sites, taking account of the relatively small numbers of participants that were not randomly selected, the following conclusions can be tentatively made:

- For the main issues of the conventional PESTLE issues, the results were broadly in line with current surveys of public opinion in Europe. For example, a Eurobarometer survey⁵ of EU citizens conducted in September 2023, “peace and security” was identified as the most pressing challenge facing partner countries (40% of respondents), followed by health (29%) and economic growth and unemployment (28%). Around one quarter mentioned democracy and human rights (26%) or climate change (25%), while 21% mentioned education.
- For those issues chosen for relevance to the Restore4Life project (Table 8), only one was rated as in a good situation: political will to invest in NBS at Vlasina (though this contrasted with a poor rating for political will for NBS);
- The attractiveness of the four sites for NBS businesses could be ranked as best in Vlasina and worst in March, though none of the sites seems especially outstanding and any initiative would meet a large range of challenges for any entrepreneur.

⁵ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2952>

TABLE 8 : STATE OF ENVIRONMENT-RELATED ISSUES IN EACH SITE

Present Condition Score
 1 - 20 = very good, measures in place and well enforced
 21 - 40 = good, measures in place, mostly enforced
 41 - 60 = moderate, measures in place, poorly enforced
 61 - 80 = bad, measures in place, no enforcement
 81 - 100 = very bad, no measures in place

	March	Rudava	Vlasina	Enisala
POLITICS				
Supportive political environment for NBS	moderate	bad	bad	bad
Political will to invest in NBS	bad	moderate	good	moderate
ECONOMICS				
Conflicts between different land users	bad	bad	bad	moderate
Converting NBS benefits into revenue	very bad	bad	moderate	moderate
Opportunities for NBS business development	very bad	bad	moderate	moderate
SOCIAL ISSUES				
Change of public awareness of NBS concept	bad	bad	moderate	moderate
Responsible company regarding biodiversity	bad	bad	moderate	moderate
TECHNOLOGY				
Need to adapt and invest capital	moderate	moderate	moderate	bad
Access to markets	moderate	bad	bad	moderate
LEGISLATION				
Reduction / elimination of environmental impacts	moderate	moderate	bad	bad
ENVIRONMENT				
Seasonal conditions	bad	bad	bad	bad
Handling hazardous materials	bad	moderate	bad	moderate
Care for protected habitats and species	moderate	moderate	bad	bad
Total number of good conditions	0	0	1	0
Total number of moderate conditions	5	5	5	8
Total number of bad conditions	6	8	7	5
Total number of very bad conditions	2	0	0	0

6 REFERENCES

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- 3 Granholm Göran, Katarina Stanoevska, Vera Lenz-Kesekamp, Roberto Russo, and Irene Matzakou (2017) PESTLE Analysis Deliverable 7.3 of the Data-Driven Bioeconomy project 732064 (H2020-ICT-2016-1 – Innovation Action). <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b77bf202&appId=PPGMS>
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